

DIGITAL IDENTITY MANAGEMENT: A KEY FACTOR ON THE PURSUIT OF PRIVACY AND THE FIGHT AGAINST CYBERCRIME

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ABSTRACT: The increasing number of actions that take place in the cyberspace, replacing traditional processes based on physical presence, has led to the transformation of identity management systems accordingly to the challenges raised by digitalisation. In this context, the emergence of a digital identity has arisen new specifications for identification processes that have been mostly covered by identity providers, who play a key role for individuals' identification in Information Society. These providers have become a focus of cyberattacks aimed to steal the personal data stored by thereof, or to directly impersonate their users. Notwithstanding the fact that identity related crime is wide spreading through different techniques in a global scale, the services provided, as well as the providers offering them, lack of a comprehensive regulation. In addition, traditional delegated identity management systems suffer from excessive data collection and centralization of information, as well as deficient security measures for ensuring data privacy.

The University of Murcia has already participated in a previous research project concerning these issues, H2020 ARIES,¹ and has continued the study through the coordination of H2020 OLYMPUS project.² These projects aim to hinder identity theft by increasing security through stronger mechanisms for verifying user's identity before providing authentication (e.g. biometrics) or adding a higher level of security for users' credentials by implementing a novel architecture based on identity provider virtualisation and password disaggregation. This paper aims to develop the legal grounds for the technologies proposed by the abovementioned EU projects, with particular attention to existing regulations, such as the GDPR or eIDAS, which may constitute the basis for developing a specific regulation for these new privacy-enhanced identification systems. Reusing the eIDAS Regulation security and interoperability rules would allow the recognition of these enhanced identity management services in the whole European Union, contributing to the Digital Single Market objective.

KEYWORDS: Digital Identity, Identity Management, Identity Theft, Data Protection, eIDAS Regulation.

Introduction

Widespread digitalization of society has arisen the need to identify individuals through networks as a building block for guaranteeing those movements or transactions which take place online. For that purpose, different models or systems for identity management (hereafter IdM) have emerged, often harming individuals' right to privacy and arising new legal issues. Data protection regulations, and particularly the General Data Protection Regulation (hereafter GDPR), have not been oblivious to the problems triggered by technological advances in the Information Society, forecasting legal tools designed to assess and, if necessary, conduct or limit innovations.

On the other hand, information and communication technologies have brought new possibilities to carry out conducts with criminal implications. In this sense, criminals have modernized their activities and have made use of the possibilities offered by the cyberspace in which each individual becomes at the same time sender and receiver "almost instantaneously" in diffuse territorial boundaries [24].

¹ <https://www.aries-project.eu/> (Grant Agreement 700085)

² <https://olympus-project.eu/> (Grant Agreement 786725)

More specifically, a large majority of digital crimes are related to identity theft [29] and the methods for their commission have been refined [23]. Nevertheless, unlike traditional identity theft, committed by physical means, the theft of the digital identity is integrated in the innovative discipline of the cyber criminology [28]. Hence, the fight against digital identity related crime require a multidisciplinary approach, involving the collaboration of technical, legal and social experts in order to assess the problem, propose solutions and in a last stage, validate them.

The aim of this paper is not only to offer some background regarding the relation between the design of IdM systems and the prevention of identity theft, but also to introduce a practical example of how two specific H2020 European research projects in the area (ARIES and OLYMPUS) propose different solutions in order to tackle the problem. In addition, besides giving a comprehensible explanation of the solutions proposed, we will focus on their legal implications, particularly how they prevent identity theft, but also which other legal concerns may arise (i.e. the impact on Data Protection and eIDAS regulations).

1. Identity Management: a new building block in the Information Society

The concept of digital identity refers to a set of attributes (or personal data), which allow to clearly identify a person through an authentication process in those movements that take place online [9]. In so far as our identity is composed by a collection of attributes that might be combined and disaggregated in different environments in support of authentication processes, the role developed by the certification entities becomes essential [39]. Considering the entity providing the service, two main models might be concluded: [10]

a) *In-house digital identities* refer to those which allow us to interact with the person or organization that has provided us with them. In this scenario there is not a sole legal entity, but the identification services work as an “in house service.” This is common in the case of financial entities, which normally rely on their own identification systems.³

Figure 1.1. IdM in-house service model
(Source: Authors, 2020)

b) *Delegated or outsourced identities* refers to those identities which allow us to interact with organizations or entities different to the ones that have provided us with them. In this scenario, we find separated legal entities whose relations might have a statutory or a contractual basis. In the first case we refer to the identity federation regulated by eIDAS, in which each Member State acts as an IdP (hereafter the IdP), but also admits and recognizes other Member States as IdPs. Regarding the second case, we would

³ For example, the bank BBVA has its own identification system, offering different authentication methods (credentials, biometrics, double factor...), depending on the online banking service the client is trying to access. Particularly, banks have focused on the challenge of verifying user's real identity at the moment of opening a new account through different mechanisms (videocall, ID document scanning...). All these processes are managed by the bank IdM services, instead of relying on an external legal entity. See, inter alia, the following site: <https://www.bbva.es/en/finanzas-vistazo/tu-guia-bbva/cuentas/metodos-identificacion.html#video-call>

be in the scenario of private legal entities, that establish their relations through a single, or multiple contracts. Hence, a legal entity, the IdP, provides with IdM services to a different legal entity, the Service Provider (hereafter the SP). This is the most common authentication method as it facilitates authentication in different places by using the same credentials, through a standardized delegated authentication process (i.e. Single Sign-On Solutions).

Figure 1.2 Delegated IdM model
(Source: Authors, 2020)

Furthermore, regarding this second scenario we can distinguish between centralized and federated IdM systems. In the first one there is a sole IdP, while in federated IdM user can access different services by using a single credential, among multiple credential providers (e.g. Facebook, Google, Amazon...). The first model main drawback is that there is a sole intermediary for all user's movements online.⁴ Nevertheless, "centralization" is a common problem for both IdM models (i.e. centralized or federated), as user's data always appear regrouped in a single IdP, affecting data security [34] and exposed, among other forms of cybercrime, to identity theft.

2. Improving IdM in the fight against cybercrime

Criminals have taken advantage of possibilities offered by the online identification systems to gain access to individuals' personal data and probably impersonate them at a later stage. One of the most common methods to commit identity theft was stealing the computer or other storage device, something that today lacks efficiency considering complex data encryption processes. Indeed, nowadays common techniques used in order to steal users' identities consist in hacking practices [32], or cracker attacks that look for an abusive access into a system. Another widely used techniques are search engine,⁵ web scraping,⁶ spoofing,⁷ or

⁴ That's however a different problem we are not going to discuss in this paper. Indeed, privileged position of the IdPs to control users' movements online might arise essential concerns regarding individuals right to privacy and data protection. There is a lot of bibliography discussing this issue as it might be Mitsilegas V. "Surveillance and Digital privacy in the Transatlantic War on Terror: The Case for a Global Privacy Regime" in *Columbia Human Rights Law Review* no.47 or Neil M. Richards, "The Dangers of Surveillance." *Harvard Law Review*, vol.126, no.7.

⁵ **Search engine** consists on the use of the power of search engines to collect information (personal data, emails, credit cards...) in order to, among other possibilities, impersonate the user at a later stage. See, inter alia, the following site: <https://techterms.com/definition/searchengine>.

⁶ **Web scraping** consist in the practice of looking for personal information in plain text, unduly forgotten between the programming language. See, inter alia, the following site: <tps://techterms.com/definition/scraping>

⁷ A **spoofing** attack takes place when a malicious party impersonates another device or user on a network in order to launch attacks against network hosts, steal data, spread malware or bypass access controls. ... Some of the

spywares.⁸ In addition, social engineering, such as phishing, smishing, vishing⁹ or pharming¹⁰ also represent a considerable percentage of attacks aimed to steal personal data [15].

On the other hand, attacks to digital identity do not limit to a specific conduct, but they can materialize in different forms distinguishing between identity theft, identity abuse and identity fraud.¹¹ In addition, authentication processes usually involve the issuance of “proofs” which normally materialize in form of tokens.¹² These tokens are presented at the time of a transaction, hence the person making use of it assumes the right to exclusive use thereof [44]. Consequently, attacks focused on the token’s issuance processes must also be taken into account when considering IdM systems vulnerabilities before identity related crime.

Furthermore, it should be noted that identity theft includes or requires different actions. First, it implies an abusive access to computer systems, the data interception and finally the use of these data. The actions of access and use have commonly been punished in most of the States’ criminal rulings, existing a “grey area” regarding the data possession. However, latest privacy concerns have also covered the unlawful possession and transfer of data as a punishable conduct [38]. This is consistent with social developments in privacy issues, so theft is not limited to economic data (e.g. bank’s information), but it includes all those referring to an individual which affect his privacy [11].

IdM tend to evolve in the light of an improved prevention from such attacks, at the time a higher degree of compliance with Data Protection Regulations is achieved, considering both, the legal and technical concepts of privacy [43]. Different techniques of encryption are used in order to assure privacy in case of loss or theft of physic equipment, fulfilling what established in article 32.1.a) of the GDPR among other legal provisions. Similarly, double storages or replicated information is avoided, at the time term of storage is limited in order to enhance data minimization principle (articles 5.1. section c) and 25.1 of the GDPR among others). In addition, Data Protection Authorities as well as private intermediaries in the area develop an important task for individuals concern in choosing strong passwords [31] or systems with two-factor authentication mechanisms, as well as avoiding data collectors on the internet.

Likewise, considering that one of the major problems of identity theft is its belated detection by the user, some mechanisms such as *Firefox Monitor* or *Google leaked-password checker* are gaining importance, enhancing internet users’ capacity of managing and safeguarding their online privacy, which in turn, minimize the possible harm of online risks [30]. On the other side, data controllers play an essential role in preventing or at least limiting the effects of identity

most common methods include IP address spoofing attacks (or web spoofing), ARP spoofing attacks and DNS server spoofing attacks. See, inter alia, the following site: <https://techterms.com/definition/spoofing>

⁸ The **spyware** consists on a software that spies a computer so it might capture information such as usernames and passwords. See, inter alia, the following site: <https://techterms.com/definition/spyware>

⁹ **Phishing** consists on the fraudulent practice of sending emails or another kind of messages (e.g. it might consist in just displaying fraudulent information on your computer screen) pretending being from reputable companies or acquaintances in order to induce individuals to reveal personal information, such as passwords and credit card numbers. The term **smishing** is used in those cases that this practice is carried out through text messages, and **vishing** in case of phone calls or voice messaged. See, inter alia, the following sites:

<https://techterms.com/definition/phishing> <https://techterms.com/definition/smishing>

¹⁰ **Pharming** consists on the practice of installing a malicious code on a personal computer or server to misdirect users to fraudulent websites without their knowledge or consent. It is considered as a form of phishing. See, inter alia, the following site: <https://techterms.com/definition/pharming>

¹¹ Following definitions given by institutions such as the UK Home Office Identity Fraud Steering, Cifas or the Commission on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice of the United Nations, we can conclude that “**identity theft**” refers to an unauthorized appropriation of identification information, while “**identity abuse**” consists on the unauthorized use of other’s identity, and “**identity fraud**” adds to this unauthorized access the aim to obtain goods or contract services.

¹² An access **token** can be defined in the context of an authentication processes a set of information that constitutes an individual’s identity for transactional purposes See, inter alia, the following site: https://developers.facebook.com/docs/facebook-login/access-tokens/?locale=es_LA

theft [33]. In this sense, controllers are obliged to determine in cases of theft or data leakage (articles 2(2), 4(7), 4(12), 33, 34 and 83(4) 4.7 of the GDPR), which data have been compromised, and communicate such information to the subjects of the processing in a clear and precise manner, indicating the nature of the conduct, the time and content of the compromised data.

Important latest research in the area have focused on the development of highly resilient architectures against direct attacks or in a radical change in the way IdM has been understood until the moment (e.g. self-sovereign identity proposals) [48]. This paper focus on the first aspect, the development of a strongly resistant architecture before attacks aimed to impersonate the user by the design of new architecture systems, which also imply a comprehensive study in legal terms in order to conduct or limit such inventions, in the light of the compliance with the European principles and regulations.

3. Main drawbacks of traditional IdPs

Traditional delegated authentication IdM systems (centralized or federated) share a common vulnerability: they appear as a single point of failure or attack [49]. Consequently, cybercriminals focus their actions on a sole objective, the IdP, which once compromised, will allow the attacker to gain access to the personal data stored in its databases or even impersonate the user in all the services connected [50]. This task becomes easier since all these legal entities act as guarantor of users' credentials for authentication processes [16], usually lacking appropriate (or at least enough) safeguards to protect passwords from cybercriminal attacks.

More specifically, in this scenario identity theft might be committed by two main different conducts:

- a) By attacking the IdP databases in order to steal users' password and then sign on in the service pretending to be the authorized user.
- b) By compromising the IdP through some form of malicious attack and issuing tokens for the cybercriminal authentication.

Figure 3.1. Traditional IdP in Single Sign-On scenario before identity theft
(Source: Authors, 2020)

Note that both conducts also apply in a scenario of data theft:

- a) The attacker can directly steal users' personal data by compromising those databases where they are stored.
- b) The attacker can also access all user's personal data by impersonating them, hence once he has authenticated, he would gain access to the user's account and therefore to all his personal information.

Following the methodology given for conducting a risk analysis ($Risk = likelihood \times impact$) [42] in a Data Protection Impact Assessment (hereafter DPIA) [26], we would obtain important risks regarding traditional IdPs architecture design:

Risk of identity theft: likelihood of identity theft (relevant) \times impact of identity theft (maximum)

Depending on security measures implemented, but in any case, it just requires compromising an IdP

Data theft: likelihood of data theft (relevant) \times impact of data theft (variable)

Depending on security measures implemented, but also of the risk of data theft

Depending on the affected data (type of access and nature of the data leaked)

From this perspective there is a clear link between identity theft and data theft, or in other words, criminal and privacy issues. Data theft becomes in many cases a consequence of identity theft, hence by limiting this first attack possibilities of data theft would also be reduced. Equally, possibilities of identity theft can be reduced by ensuring privacy rules compliance, particularly but not limited to data minimization and proportionality principles. According to the first one, the data stored by the IdP would be pertinent and limited to the strictly necessary purposes for which they were collected [40], that is to say, a forthcoming authentication process. In addition, proportionality principle envisages that the measures implemented should not exceed what it is necessary to achieve the purposes or objectives of the processing [20], hence not only the amount of the data stored, but also the adopted actions affecting this data (e.g. the use of encryption techniques, duplicated databases...) must be considered.

Finally, regarding the service, in this architecture design user will require at every moment the availability of the IdP in order to proceed in his authentication, so there is also a high chance of system failure.

4. New proposals for improved IdM: The EU Horizon 2020 ARIES and OLYMPUS projects

4.1. ARIES approach

The project ARIES (conducted between the years 2016-2018) presented an innovative authentication mechanism at that moment: the use of biometrics. For that purpose, the user has to perform in a first stage a biometric enrolment (i.e. facial or voice enrollment) for in a later moment, perform a live acquisition of his biometric feature to compare it with the information previously stored [2].

Furthermore, ARIES had foreseen two different use cases. The first one was an e-commerce scenario in which the user attempts to buy products in a website performing authentication and if necessary, a live biometric authentication on his mobile device. The second one refers to an airport passport control scenario, where the possibility for passengers to use this authentication method at the boarding gate by performing a live biometric test at the camera and screen of the boarding terminal system had been envisaged. Then, the user will share the biometric token stored in the smartphone obtained during enrolment leaked to his real identity

(e.g. to his national identity document) to the biometric verifier service deployed in the boarding terminal for their comparison. This technique could also be deployed in order to confirm the user has a valid boarding pass for shopping at the terminal or even to check his age without disclosing any additional personal data [3].

Biometric authentication systems allow recognition of an individual by considering his biological or behavioral features. The main advantage of biometrics is that they are unique and personal, enabling strong authentication [13]. However, it must be noted that these characteristics are permanent and cannot be renewed, therefore the process itself needs to be properly handled to avoid biometric data leakage, representing a potential security threat. Nevertheless, risks of theft are significantly less than other authentication methods (e.g. passwords), as it normally requires a personal knowledge of the person aiming to impersonate, as well as an appropriate method to replicate this physical feature [22].

Biometric data are however included by article 9.1 of the GDPR among the special category of personal data. Therefore, its processing shall not be permitted unless one of the circumstances envisaged in section two of the article applies. Moreover, considering the high risks inherently attached to the processing of biometric data, the conduction of a DPIA will be mandatory in many cases to justify the proportionality of using this data instead of a different mechanism which might imply a lower risk [36].

In the case of the project ARIES, to minimize these privacy concerns, biometric information required during enrollment process was stored at the user's mobile device. Equally, during authentication process, data are discarded afterwards, just storing an audit log in order to fulfill the Law Enforcement Authorities requirements [4].

4.2. OLYMPUS approach

The project OLYMPUS (envisaged between the years 2018-2021) has introduced a new architecture design for delegated IdM: the IdP virtualization or the virtual IdP (hereafter vIdP). More specifically, this architecture consists on the distribution of the task of a single IdP, the vIdP, among several IdPs which still appear as one for the user.

Figure 4.2.1. OLYMPUS architecture design
(Source: Authors, 2020)

OLYMPUS distributed architecture proposal constitutes an improvement from the point of view of software security, hampering the success of those cyberattacks aiming to steal individuals' identity and normally making a fraudulent use thereof. For that purpose, user's password appears disaggregated among the several IdPs, enabling the distributed authentication, or in other words, the necessary collaboration of all the IdPs for the token issuance [14].

Regarding identity theft, this would mean that the attacker will need to have the control over all the structure as user's password (necessary for the token issuance) appears disaggregated

through thereof. Moreover, OLYMPUS includes a proactive security mechanism called “Key-Resharing” which allows password redistribution, posing different scenarios before the attacker, thus in the event he successfully compromise one of the IdPs, the “segment” of password obtained will just remain valid for a short period of time as these “segments of password” will redistribute again,¹³ assuring the IdPs honesty [5].

Figure 4.2.2. OLYMPUS proactive security mechanisms
(Source: Authors, 2020)

Furthermore, OLYMPUS combines this innovative architecture with the objective of an “oblivious IdM”, so user’s privacy is enhanced by limiting the possibilities of the IdP to control his movements online. Until the moment, this has been successfully achieved in one of the use cases, the Mobile Driver’s License offline modality, through the generation of credentials which are stored in user’s mobile device to be presented in a further authentication process in order to prove the attributes contained in that document (the use case is envisaged for the event of age proof) [35].

OLYMPUS final purpose is to develop that “highly resistant” architecture before cyberattacks, maintaining the use of passwords, but adding security to this traditional authentication method by the introduction of a new architecture design and complex cryptographic protocols [12]. This is consistent with the imperative of privacy by design or the introduction of guarantees for the protection of individuals’ rights and freedoms in the processing of their personal data since the first stage of systems and products development. At the same time those events which might affect privacy must be foreseen prior their materialization, or what is the same, the introduction of proactive safeguards or mechanisms which anticipate to threats, identifying weakness to neutralize or minimize risks [41].

5. Widely recognized IdM systems and their privacy concerns

The final purpose of all IdM systems is to provide users’ identification before the maximum extent possible of services or relying parties. However, this requires considering those regulations in charge of determining what types or means for identification are valid or recognized. In that sense, not only National Law, but also EU Law must be considered, as it is the case of the eIDAS regulation, which has an essential importance in the context of the Digital Single Market [27].

The aim of the eIDAS regulation is to enhance trust in electronic transactions in the internal market by providing a common basis for secure electronic interactions between citizens, businesses and public authorities. For that purpose, the eIDAS regulation establishes a set of common high-level rules or principles, and technical standards, completed by technical

¹³ This mechanism has essential importance for the prevention of brute-force attacks as it is described in the article “The OLYMPUS Architecture—Oblivious Identity Management for Private User-Friendly Services” accessible at the following address: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/20/3/945/htm>

specifications that allow different eID systems to interoperate. This results in a set of technical requirements, set of levels of assurance, and particularly, a set of minimum identification data [17] in support of a European-wide public identity federation

More specifically, the implementation of the Interoperability Framework relies on the eIDAS nodes. Indeed, in the context of a cross-border identification process, the eIDAS nodes facilitate the “translation” of the tokens to make them compatible with the eID schemes, or in other words, eIDAS nodes “translate” incoming SAML requests from the SP into authentication requests compliant with the eID scheme of end user’s country of origin [19].

Figure 5.1. Cross-border authentication process through eIDAS nodes (Source: Authors, 2020)

On the other hand, the eIDAS regulation includes two main different contents. First, it stipulates a framework for accessing public services in the European Union by using an identification service of their own Member State, and second, it creates an internal market for trust services defining their conditions as well as their possible classification [18]. Regarding this second objective, the eIDAS regulation offers a list of those services considered as trust services.¹⁴ However, among these services the eIDAS regulation does not expressly include the electronic identification as a trust service, by the fact that it constitutes a prerogative of the State [25]. Consequently, different legal regimes can coexist in a single State, and an electronic identification service might be considered as a public service, a trust service or even a private service regarding specific permissions established by the State [6].

Nevertheless, certain trust services allow identification, as it is the case of certificates for electronic signature, which in the end provide an electronic attestation that binds the identification data with the name of that person, in support of his/her electronic signature [7]. It must be noted, however, that these electronic certificates have to be admitted by National Law for authentication purposes and then notified as a form of electronic identification means. Otherwise, they would be excluded of the eIDAS regulation [8].

Regarding authentication processes, both, federated and non-federated methods can be employed under eIDAS regulation, and despite the fact that federated authentication mechanisms are generally easier to use, the downside however is that all information

¹⁴Article 3 (16) eIDAS regulation defines **trust services** as: “an electronic service normally provided for remuneration which consists of: (a) the creation, verification, and validation of electronic signatures, electronic seals or electronic time stamps, electronic registered delivery services and certificates related to those services, or (b) the creation, verification and validation of certificates for website authentication; or (c) the preservation of electronic signatures, seals or certificates related to those services.

regarding authentication will pass through that federation, causing major privacy and security concerns [37].

According to the European Data Protection Supervisor, policies promoting privacy enhancing technologies and strategies should be within the priorities of the EU agenda [21], hence new developments have to find a balance between a wide usability and privacy. The project ARIES introduced an innovative approach in that sense as it is the creation of partial derived identities,¹⁵ which can be presented before the different SPs maintaining user's privacy, while keeping their validity for those transactions which require a strong identification. The substitution of the respective document by these derived ARIES identities maintaining legal certainty, will require the definition of these services as a new trust service.

In the case of OLYMPUS, different possibilities are currently being discussed, from the use of pseudonyms before the different SPs, possibility that will be directly implementable in the current EU framework prior authorization in each Member State, to the possibility of reusing derived identities [1]. Furthermore, one of the main contributions from the OLYMPUS project to the eIDAS Regulation consists in enhancing the security measures set forth in its article 8, which have been developed by Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/1502 of 8 September 2015 on setting out minimum technical specifications and procedures for assurance levels for electronic identification means pursuant to article 8(3) of Regulation (EU) N° 910/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market. Concretely, the OLYMPUS protocols could contribute to implement levels of assurance substantial or high with a higher level of privacy for the users.

However, achieving compatibility between the GDPR and the eIDAS regulation presents some difficulties. In this sense, the Interoperability Framework requires a minimum data set. This also excludes the possibility of implementing selective disclosure for services that require less attributes than those in the minimum dataset [45]. Equally, regarding pseudonymization, the minimum data set required by eIDAS alongside with the pseudonym, will never satisfy the GDPR definition of pseudonymized data [46].

Consequently, even if eIDAS is expected to comply with Data Protection Goals and facilitate privacy by design, as it states in its article 12 c), the reality is that it is arguable if the Interoperability Framework lowers the level of data protection guaranteed by some national eID schemes [47].

Conclusions and further discussion

The improvement of IdM affects from the data protection, to the prevention of cybercrime and the realization of a Single Digital Market in the framework of the European Union. The achievement of these objectives relies on the result of progressing together, the professionals of different areas in the task of finding appropriate and balanced solutions to the problematics emerged.

Regulations cannot be adopted in a radical attempt to solve the problem, ignoring social and economic realities as well as latest technological developments. This paper offers two clear examples of the existing feedback between technology and Law, or more specifically: how the Law conducts technological developments, and at the same time how these pose new scenarios which may promote new regulations or, at least, adapt the existing ones.

¹⁵ **Derived identities** consist in the creation of different identities from a former identity, normally a valid identity, that might proof separated attributes of the individual.

Likewise, it is essential to achieve balanced solutions, assessing risks in order to determine the most appropriate proposal. The current panorama is the result of an uncontrolled evolution, which is however encountering nowadays more limits for the protection of valuables goods, rights and freedoms. The GDPR constitutes a crucial representation of those limits, returning individuals the power over their own data, at the time it institutes a meaningful, and adapted to the current time, right to privacy.

However, regulations cannot remain unchangeable, but they must be adapted to the current state at each moment of their object. This is particularly evident when it comes to those laws whose object is referred to technological related content, as these tools evolve certainly so quickly that force Law to adapt its requirements and safeguards at a higher speed than legal experts are used to.

Regarding IdM evolution, we consider that each model or solution pose a decisive question. Indeed, perfect solutions are still far to exist, hence we have to decide if for example, a greater usability might justify a wider data processing or the processing of personal data that involves a higher risk (as it is the case of biometrics). It is clear that the solution must be obtained case per case, but maybe by studying and combining thereof, we can set the bases for future increasingly better and widely recognized IdM systems.

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